

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS VOLUME 15 (2022)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2022,
vol. 15

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

THE EVOLUTION OF INDONESIAN CHINESE POLITICAL CULTURE IN NORTH SUMATRA PROVINCE IN THE NEW ORDER ERA AND POST REFORM: LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

The study of political culture often places the structure of the political system as a catalyst to shape political behavior. This study explores changes in the political culture of one of the ethnic minorities in Indonesia, namely the Chinese ethnicity during two different political systems. The political system in the New Order era and in the post-reformation period is used as a comparison to see the evolution of Chinese ethnic political culture in Indonesia and specifically in North Sumatra Province. In collecting information and data, this paper uses a literature study. Books, articles and research reports related to ethnic Chinese in the political arena were used as data sources. The results of the study found that ethnic Chinese in the arena of non-democratic political systems will show passive behavior. In the political arena democracy will become active. The evolution of political culture from passive to active largely depends on an open political system and internal and external political actors who attract them to the political arena.

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Keywords: Chinese ethnicity, political culture, ethnic minorities, political behavior.

Introduction

In the long historical record of the existence of Chinese ethnicity in Indonesia, it can be photographed into seven perspectives in viewing the position of the Chinese ethnicity in four eras (pre-independence, Old Order, New Order and Post-Reformation Era), namely: 1) ethnic immigrants, 2) minority population, 3) nationalism identity, 4) victims of state discrimination, 5) victims of violence, 6) victims of exclusion and 7) the euphoria of political freedom. Entering the period of freedom in politics given the post-Reformation era, every Indonesian citizen has the same rights in various fields. This study aims to analyze the evolution of Chinese ethnic political culture in Indonesia in the Post-Reformation era and the choice of political channels in the electoral political arena. This study is considered important starting from the assumption that political freedom for ethnic Chinese in Indonesia has only been felt by ethnic Chinese since the reform era. The next assumption is that the understanding of politics for ethnic Chinese occurs when democracy moves quickly as if "forcing" ethnic Chinese political awareness to be formed.

The study of the involvement of Chinese Indonesians in the electoral political arena only began when democracy was chosen to replace the authoritarian system through a mass movement carried out by Indonesian student elements with a mass movement called the "reform movement". In the wider political area, in fact, the Chinese have played their role in the political area since the pre-independence era of Indonesia, which can be traced from the studies conducted. Darini (2008) related to ethnic Chinese nationalism. Yang (2001) on how the ethnic Chinese negotiated a new identity within a new country. The involvement of the Chinese in the political area during the Old Order era can be read by Zhou (2015) on the position of the Indonesian Chinese in the ebb and flow of the relationship between the Indonesian state and the Chinese state. Koning (2007) explores the role of ethnic Chinese in the political economy.

In the New Order era, a study conducted by Chong (2015) explored the relationship of ethnic Chinese businessmen to power at the local level. Chua (2004) The position of Chinese Indonesians in the dynamics of the national political economy. Then in the context of the Post-Reformation era, research on the involvement of ethnic Chinese in the political area is increasing because in this era freedom in the social and political fields has only been obtained by the Chinese. A

number of studies in the Post-Reformation era can read works Freedman (2003) exploring the formation of ethnic Chinese political organizations. Siddik (2010) ethnic Chinese social movements in response to equal rights after the end of the New Order era. Setijadi (2016) ethnic Chinese political identity. Ibrahim (2013); Juliastutik (2010) Chinese ethnic political behavior. Sinaga et al., (2018) competition between fellow ethnic Chinese legislative candidates in the General Election. Lan (2017) writes about the position of Chinese Indonesians in the social and political fields in the influence of interactions between Indonesia and China.

From various previous studies that have been described above, this study argues that ethnic Chinese have different political responses in each era of government and can even be different in each place. the response reflects their political culture. This study was conducted to fill in the gaps from previous research that had never explored the evolution of ethnic Chinese political culture at the local level, which specifically took place in the province of North Sumatra. This study uses the theory of Pye & Verba (1965) to help understand the political culture that occurs in the ethnic Chinese community in the province of North Sumatra. The purpose of this paper is to explore the evolution of Chinese ethnic political culture in the province of North Sumatra in two eras (the New Order era and the post-reform era). This study argues that in these two eras Indonesia adopted a different political system. The basic difference between the two eras lies in the democratic values that were recognized in the post-reform era but were not recognized in the new order era. Then on the other hand in the segmentation of ethnic communities, it is not the same as responding to political changes. This study takes a different position from the theoretical aspect. Previous research tends to understand the formation of ethnic political culture occurs from the internal aspect of the community in responding to the environment, but this study tries to understand political culture and its evolution through the external aspect of ethnicity. This study will confirm the theory of Pye & Verba (1965) which links psychological and sociological aspects to attitudes and beliefs in shaping people's political behavior.

Method

This paper uses a qualitative method which is described descriptively. This paper uses a literature study to answer the research questions in this paper. According to Creswell (2014) qualitative methods are relevant to understanding phenomena related to interactions, behaviors, processes in a human environment

to get meaning. This paper uses data from various books related to Chinese ethnicity as research subjects in historical, cultural, social, economic and political aspects that review Chinese ethnicity in Indonesia and in North Sumatra Province. To strengthen the method of this paper, a book by Halperin & Heath (2012: 1) on political research methods is used to narrate a complex and controversial phenomenon in exploring the political behavior of ethnic Chinese in Indonesia.

Discussion

1. Indonesian Chinese Ethnic Political Culture

Pye & Verba (1965) provided the concept of political culture related to aspects of attitudes, sentiments and cognitions that govern the political behavior of a society. Every community has boundaries and differences in political culture because each community has its own personality, knowledge and feelings in interpreting politics. The boundaries in interpreting politics are strongly influenced by basic factors of dynamic psychology in the form of political inheritance from previous generations, finding political identity independently, adapting to the current legal regulations (see dalam Pye & Verba, 1965: 7). Political culture is conceptually understood as attitudes/responses and beliefs in responding to a political activity. With this conceptualization, this paper explores the attitude/response of Chinese ethnicity in the electoral arena in the form of political choice actions to vote and be elected.

The process of cultural evolution takes place in the social structure of society as a response to changing times. These responses touch changes in certain aspects of traditional norms that are considered no longer relevant to be maintained (see Porta & Diani, 2006: 13). In the context of the changes in Indonesia's political system that took place after the New Order brought new norms through the concept of democracy. The concept of democracy which then moves to all areas of life in the end is faced with traditional values. In the end, new values in democracy that are considered positive for the progress of traditional values become important consumptions in responding to changing times. This condition is clearly seen in the freedom to make political choices in elections.

Pye (1965) explains that political culture on a micro scale is carried out to interpret psychological aspects and individual political behavior, while on a macro scale it observes aspects of political sociology (see Pye & Verba, 1965: 8) Based on this concept, Pye theoretically highlights aspects of psychology and sociology to

portray political culture. Based on Pye's (1965) theoretical concept of political culture, the study believes that there has been an evolution of ethnic Chinese political culture in Indonesia. Specifically, based on Pye's (1965) theory which emphasizes that political behavior is influenced by psychological and sociological aspects, with the different demographic and geographical postures in each region in Indonesia, this study assumes that in the context of the province of North Sumatra, the evolution of the political culture of the Chinese ethnic community has its own characteristics. in the process of the evolution of political culture.

2. The Evolution of Chinese Ethnic Political Culture in North Sumatra Province

A number of empirical study literatures such as ethnic Chinese find restrictions in social and political activities. State policies in the New Order era positioned the Chinese ethnicity in the arena of private sector economic activity. This policy is seen by the new order as an assimilation program effort, but the view from the other side shows discrimination against ethnic Chinese in every region in Indonesia. Portrait of Chinese ethnic social life in North Sumatra province.

At the end of 1998, the year the New Order regime resigned, a number of ethnic Chinese elites began to prepare to form formal political channels in the form of political parties. This situation is reflected in the writings of Freedman (2003: 444-445) which records the presence of the Chinese Indonesian Reform Party and the Indonesian Assimilation Party in 1998. In the local context in the province of North Sumatra during the New Order era, ethnic Chinese political activities were detected through written notes Faraidiany (2016); Mahdalena (2012); Sarumpaet (2009); Humaizi, Ermansyah, & Sinaga (2018); Chong (2015); Arofah & Nugrahajati (2014); Wu Ling (2014); Setiawan (2013); (Humaizi, Yusuf, & Sinaga (2019); Chua (2008); Sinaga, Warella, Yuwanto, & Setiyono (2019); Damanik (2017). All of this writing gives meaning to the presence, desires and challenges of the Chinese ethnic in the political arena in the province of North Sumatra which influences the formation of their political culture.

In the course of the elections to elect candidates for members of the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) of North Sumatra Province in the post-New Order era (election 1999 to 2014 elections) based on a study conducted Sinaga et al. (2019) it was seen that there was an increase in the quantity of ethnic Chinese. to contest as a candidate for members of the North Sumatra Provincial DPRD. In addition, the evaluation carried out in the study of Sinaga et al.

(2019: 74-75) shows a shift in the choice of party political channels from initially tending to advance from nationalist parties to then dispersed into two party ideologies, namely nationalist religious parties and nationalist parties. In the segmentation of the contestation arena, ethnic Chinese candidates in the province of North Sumatra tend to be penetrated in urban constituencies. The city of Medan as one of the cities targeted by ethnic Chinese contestants who competed for positions as members of the provincial DPRD even the quantity of contestants from ethnic Chinese seemed enthusiastic in the election of members of the Medan City DPRD (see Sinaga et al., 2018).

In the political arena in the regional head election (Pilkada), several ethnic Chinese community organizations have participated in participating as support groups for regional head candidates. For example, in the 2015 Medan city election, Humaizi et al.(2019) research found the active involvement of Chinese ethnic community organizations (ormas). The involvement of mass organizations as support groups in the local elections is seen in various regions with various ethnic segmentation backgrounds. The passive Chinese political behavior in the New Order era then shifted to active political behavior as a natural evolution of Chinese ethnic political culture in responding to changes in the political system. The change in the political system from non-democratic to democratic in the post-reformation period (2004-2019) has shaped the evolution of ethnic Chinese political culture into new behaviors and new beliefs in understanding ongoing political realities and potential implications in other fields. In other words, the evolution of Chinese ethnic political culture shifted from passive political behavior to active.

The political behavior of ethnic Chinese in the post-reformation era shows that active political participation does not only occur at the personal level but also at the level of community institutions such as in the form of ethnic, religious and professional-based community organizations. Naturally, the situation in democratic life broadens the horizons and hopes for each element individually and in the community to achieve the desired state. One of the least desirable conditions is the preservation of the attributes of the traditional identity of the ethnic community, the security and prosperity of fellow ethnic groups. Davidson & Henley (2007: 25) argue that in the Indonesian context, ethnic solidarity tends to be formed by groups or institutions that have education and political knowledge. This happened because in the past the colonial nation tended to close the space for the existence of local customs.

Conclusion

Research on ethnic minorities often boils down to questions about the rights and obligations derived from the state. Behavioral studies of ethnic minorities in various aspects of life such as economic, social, cultural and political are always influenced by the way the state places their position in a policy. More specifically, the political behavior of ethnic minorities tends to be the same in responding to changes in state policy in various fields. Individual attitudes that lead to the collective spirit of the group as a sign of the nature of social beings. The Chinese are no exception as an ethnic minority in Indonesia. The evolution of Chinese ethnic political culture in terms of political behavior and political choices is a response given to changes in political conditions that occur in every era of government. The evolution of political culture tends to lead from passive to active political behavior when the political system is open, active political behavior changes to passive political behavior in a closed political system. Responses to changes in the political system that occur will always present their own perceptions and calculations for each individual, including for ethnic minorities and even ethnic majorities in each region. It's just that in every production country, policies are always faced with various interests that need attention. In this situation the priority scale always prioritizes the good for the wider community.

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